

FADS AND FAST CASH – AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE SOU SOU SCHEMES IN TRINIDAD AND TOBAGO

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- *Integrated logistics at Rose Acre Farms: Implications for sustainable competitive advantage.* (Research Gate). DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15725.95200

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- *Modelling the “new normal” for Micro and Small Enterprises during Covid-19.* (Blog Post, 13/05/2020) <https://gisellelawrence.wixsite.com/busconsultancy/blog>
- *Covid-19 vaccination policy considerations for employers* (Page post, 16/07/2021) <https://www.facebook.com/pg/SGChamberTT/posts/>

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ABSTRACT

The lure of fad-like sou sou schemes promising fast cash has been gaining high momentum and popularity in Trinidad and Tobago, despite the obvious risks (Basant 2020; Singletary 2020). This research elucidated the phenomenon by using extant motivation and behavioural theories and used these to refine the Consumer Behaviour Model for a Fad (Kotler et al. 2013).

The Model shows that fads often take advantage of some unmet need (McLeod 2018). It also assumes that consumers do not always make rational and informed decisions; they are sometimes prone to informational influence and may irrationally copy the decisions of others (Bikhchandani, Hirshleifer, and Welch 1992). These can be explained by the theories of *Information Adoption*, *Information Cascades*, *Herd Behaviour* and *Risk Preference* (Balcilar and Demirer 2015; Bikhchandani et al. 1992, 1998; Chong, Liu, and Zhu 2017; Morone and Samanidou 2008; Shen, Zhang, and Zhao 2016; Wang, 2016).

It was therefore recommended that the Government of Trinidad and Tobago regulate these sou sou schemes to deter criminals from using the sou sou as a front for their money laundering enterprises, and to keep citizens safe from scammers.

Tags: Sou Sou, Pyramid scheme, Fad, Information adoption, Information cascade, herd behaviour.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

For many persons today, living from day to day is fraught with numerous challenges and strife. Many people have to contend with falling oil prices which increases the cost of living, stagnant or reduced salaries, large income inequalities, unemployment, lack of education, ever increasing food prices, hunger, poverty, and high levels of crime (Loop News 2020a, 2020b; Loudenback and Jackson 2018). Additionally, the recent restrictions placed on businesses and individuals during the Covid-19 pandemic makes the situation more dire (Ministry of Health Trinidad and Tobago n.d.; Sambrano 2020; Taitt 2020; World Health Organisation 2020).

It is no wonder then that the lure of fast cash holds so much power and sway, as money can easily be used to resolve persons' immediate needs such as, to pay bills or, to purchase food. However, accessing loans from commercial banks are difficult, and even more so for persons below a certain income bracket or for the unemployed (Appel 2008). Recently, this has led to an explosion of various sou sou type pyramid schemes throughout Trinidad and Tobago (Basant 2020; Gonzales 2020; Singletary 2020). These schemes all promise a high rate of return for a small financial investment, with many of its advocates portraying these schemes as an option for the poor to become financially independent in a relatively short space of time (Gonzales 2020; Singletary 2020).

1.2 Problem statement

Despite numerous raids on the popular '*Drug Sou Sou*' (DSS) by the Trinidad and Tobago Police Service (Basant, 2020), and the crash of many flower-type gifting sou sous resulting in many citizens losing their hard-earned money (Gonzales 2020), this fad has exploded into a viral sensation with new versions being propagated every day (Singletary 2020).

1.3 Research Questions

This therefore begs the question – *why do the citizens of Trinidad and Tobago continue to support this fad, despite the explicit warnings provided by the Central bank and other financial institutions, and at the risk of losing money should it crash?*

This research will also attempt to answer these other pressing questions:

1. *What are the physiological determinants of this fad?* That is, what situations will make a person more likely to join one of these hybrid sou sous?
2. *What are the psychological implications of this fad?* That is, what are the person's thought processes that makes him want to engage in the sou sou scheme?

1.4 Aim of the research

This research therefore aims to elucidate the current phenomenon by using extant motivation and behavioural theories in the field of marketing and to use these to refine the Consumer Behaviour Model for a Fad.

1.5 Research Methodology

This explanatory research will take an abductive approach to the literature and will involve the analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data gathered from primary and secondary sources. This approach is being taken since not much is known or written about this fad in Trinidad and Tobago.

1.6 Significance of the study

This research will enable policy makers and law enforcement officials in Trinidad and Tobago to fully understand why citizens are getting caught in these schemes, so that they can draft policies to safeguard citizens from criminals abusing the system. Financial institutions can also use this information to develop financial services and packages targeted towards low-income households to provide some short-term financial relief.

This study will also help citizens to become more aware of these schemes and to understand their own irrational behaviour.

Finally, this study will add to extant body of literature surrounding consumer behaviour for fads and will provide a solid foundation upon which further groundwork can emerge.

This therefore concludes the introduction. The following section will discuss the literature reviewed.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 What is a Sou Sou?

The literature defines a *sou sou* as an informal savings group where members agree to contribute a certain amount of money to a fixed pool and receive the total amount of the pooled cash as a lump sum (also called a “hand”) at agreed upon times (Appel 2008; Maynard 1996; Mtshali 2017). So basically, it is an alternative financial system for saving, with the emphasis being on its *informal nature*, as it forms part of the informal economy.

The sou sou has existed for quite a long period of time. According to the literature, the term is derived from the Yoruba “*esusu*,” which Maynard (1996) described as a sophisticated African rotating credit system. The sou sou is highly resilient—it was brought over to the Caribbean by African slaves and despite not being practiced during the 300 years of African slavery it has re-emerged among their descendants today (Maynard, 1996; Mtshali, 2017). Furthermore, while the sou sou came from Africa, it is not practiced by just Africans or Afro-Caribbean people alone, as Mtshali (2017) pointed out, it is also popular among the Asian and Latino communities as well.

2.2 How does it work?

In the traditional sou sou, *each member will receive the exact amount they paid out*; there is *no interest earned* on the instalments, and the total each person receives is exactly the same as the total paid out (Appel 2008; Maynard 1996; Mtshali 2017).

So, for example, if there are five persons in the sou sou group, each contributing \$100 each week, then in the first week, one person will receive a lump sum, or “hand”, of \$500. In the second week the other assigned person will receive \$500, and so on until the last person receives their “hand”. (See Figure 1 on page 9)

Figure 1. Basic sou sou operation for a 5-person group with each member receiving the exact amount they paid out (created for this research using Appel 2008; Maynard 1996; Mtshali 2017).

2.3 Benefits of the sou sou

In Africa, the absence of a formal banking system made the esusu indispensable for the common man to obtain a lump sum of money in the shortest possible time, to meet his needs and fulfil his financial obligations (Appel 2008; Maynard 1996; Mtshali 2017). Similarly, in today's society, despite having a functioning banking system, the sou sou's appeal lies in its ability to quickly provide a large sum of cash without the bureaucracy, paperwork, and stress, of trying to obtain a bank loan (Appel 2008; Mtshali 2017; Singletary 2020).

As Mtshali (2017) writes, people commonly join sou sours to purchase expensive goods/services, to go on vacations, to open businesses, to further their education, or to use as a down payment for real estate or vehicles. Furthermore, people who would not normally be able to access a loan, such as those with a poor credit rating or those below a certain income bracket, would still be able to obtain a lump sum of cash from a sou sou (Mtshali 2017). However, the most important benefit for joining a traditional sou sou instead of a bank, is that it encourages and fosters financial self-discipline, and gets one into the positive habit of saving (Mtshali 2017).

2.4 Risks of sou sous

Of course, no man-made system is without its share of risks, and a sou sou is no different. While sou sous are legal, they can be used by fraudsters for evil intent (Appel 2008; Maynard 1996; Mtshali 2017). Generally, the risks associated with traditional sou sous involves the non-payment of instalments by members, especially for the final hand (Maynard 1996; Mtshali 2017). To mitigate this risk, traditional sou sous are usually conducted with close and trusted family members and friends (Appel 2008; Maynard 1996; Mtshali 2017).

While sou sous are legal, *pyramid schemes are always illegal.*

2.5 What is a pyramid scheme?

A pyramid scheme is an illegal business structure, shaped like a pyramid, where money paid by new recruits at the base of the pyramid are used to pay subsequent investors higher up (Gonzales 2020; Jarvis 2000; Vander Nat and Keep, 2002). (See Figure 2 below)

Figure 2. Typical structure of a pyramid scheme (created for this research using Jarvis 2000; Vander Nat and Keep 2002).

Pyramid schemes are extremely risky ventures as there is generally no real investment of the money within the scheme; money is simply moved from the lower levels to the top. According to a joint press release issued by various financial bodies in Trinidad and Tobago such as, the Financial Intelligence Unit, the Securities and Exchange Commission, and the Central Bank, a pyramid scheme often relies on a continuous flow of new recruits for the scheme to persist, with each new recruit being promised an unbelievably high rate of return on their initial investment (Gonzales 2020). To this, Jarvis (2000), and Vander Nat and Keep (2002) agrees.

The absence of genuine investment and accountability makes a pyramid scheme particularly dubious and unsustainable in the long-term. Pyramid schemes are a convenient way for criminals to launder the proceeds of their criminal activities as it is often difficult for the authorities to ascertain where the money originated (Gonzales 2020; Vander Nat and Keep 2002). As mentioned by Jarvis (2000), Albanian companies that engaged in pyramid schemes in the early 1990s, also used the proceeds of the funds to engage in illegal smuggling, prostitution, arms dealing, and drug trafficking. Even recently, the Trinidad and Tobago Police Commissioner lamented that criminals were using pyramid schemes as a façade for money-laundering (Basant 2020).

Moreover, it is *mathematically impossible* for pyramids to be sustained forever, and somewhere along the line people will invariably lose their money (Basant 2020; Gonzales 2020; Jarvis 2000; Singletary 2020; Vander Nat and Keep 2002).

Whereas proponents of the scheme may argue that pyramids can be viable and self-sustaining so long as there is always a wider base of new recruits, in reality however, the pool of new recruits invariably shrinks, or stalls, over time thereby leading to the collapse of the entire structure (Gonzales 2020; Jarvis 2000; Vander Nat and Keep 2002).

While the collapse of pyramids can be disappointing for higher tiered members who may lose money due to the delay in payments from subordinates, it is even more devastating for the vast majority of recruits at the bottom who stand to lose everything (Vander Nat and Keep 2002). As warned by various fraud agencies, once a pyramid scheme collapses, it will disappear along with all the money that was invested into it (Gonzales 2020; Singletary 2020).

2.6 Illegal pyramid schemes versus Multilevel Marketing schemes

There are other controversial but legitimate structures that resemble a pyramid scheme for example, companies that use Multilevel Marketing (Kotler et al. 2013; Vander Nat and Keep, 2002; Wharton University of Pennsylvania 2011). According to Vander Nat and Keep (2002) and Wharton University of Pennsylvania (2011) Multilevel Marketing (MLM) is a strategy used by some direct selling companies such as AVON, Herbalife, and Amway, as a way to increase the sales of their range of goods and services, and often involves repeat purchases by independent distributors and their downline, that is, new recruits.

MLM companies have complex compensation packages, but basically pays their independent distributors a commission from two major means—through the distributors’ own personal sales, and through the sales of the distributors’ downline (Kotler et al. 2013; Vander Nat and Keep 2002; Wharton University of Pennsylvania 2011). While the compensation and recruitment look like a pyramid, they are differentiated by their *core focus*, which is, *increasing the retail sales value* of their products, while pyramid schemes mainly focus on increasing new recruits regardless of the sales value (Vander Nat and Keep 2002; Wharton University of Pennsylvania 2011).

Additionally, while many independent distributors in MLM schemes may never realistically achieve top compensation as they are led to believe, they are still better off than those in illegal pyramid schemes where the vast majority lose everything financially (Jarvis 2000; Vander Nat and Keep 2002; Wharton University of Pennsylvania 2011).

Since this distinction is so narrow and not so easily distinguishable, MLM companies have now become tightly regulated in the USA, while over in China, they have been made illegal (Vander Nat and Keep 2002).

2.7 Life cycle of a pyramid scheme

Based on Jarvis (2000) the lifecycle of a pyramid scheme can be thought of having four stages:

1. ***Initial investment*** - Early investors are lured into the scheme which promises high rewards for a small initial investment over a short period of time.
2. ***Growth*** - Increased advertising and promotion of the scheme follows, and more people invest. Their money is used to pay earlier investors, who may themselves also reinvest. “Most people, however, remain skeptical” (Jarvis 2000, 7).
3. ***Last-minute rush*** - More investors come on board, even the skeptical ones, as the scheme seems successful. Many rush to get a piece of the pie before the scheme collapses.
4. ***Collapse*** - The scheme eventually collapses as payment becomes stalled and investors lose confidence and try to recoup their money, but never do get it back. (See Figure 3)

Figure 3. *Lifecycle of a typical Pyramid Scheme (Adapted from Jarvis 2000, 7).*

When depicted as a diagram, the lifecycle of a pyramid scheme clearly resembles that of a marketing fad.

2.8 What is a fad?

According to Kotler et al. (2013)—marketing exists to fulfil an unmet need, and fads do just that. The Marketing expert opines that fads are a type of *current or popular style “that come quickly into the public view, are adopted with great zeal, peak early, and decline very fast”* (Kotler et al. 2013, 393). (See Figure 4 below)

Figure 4. *Lifecycle of a fad. (Kotler et al. 2013, 392).*

In this definition, the authors stress on the *short and unsustainable nature of a fad* (Kotler et al. 2013). The Authors also note that fads tend to attract *early adopters* and *thrill seekers* (the initial risk takers who are rewarded for their early entry into the scheme) who are searching for something new and unique however, once this need becomes satisfied, the fad is no longer useful, and it quickly dies (Kotler et al. 2013). Similarly, with a pyramid scheme –great interest and zeal is first garnered through the use of advertising to attract new investors however, once payment stops or stalls, the system comes crashing as investors try to recoup their money (Jarvis 2000).

While researchers may not agree on the exact causes of a fad, they have conducted many studies into the subject in an attempt to understand and predict human behaviour. This is important to note because *understanding the motives and causes behind fads, will also aid in the understanding of same for pyramid schemes*. Some of the theories used to explain fad behaviour are presented in the following section.

2.9 Understanding Fad Behaviour

2.9.1 General model of consumer behaviour. Since a fad is described in marketing terms as filling an unmet need, then the first place to begin understanding fad behaviour is by looking at how consumers generally behave to have those needs met. According to Kotler et al. (2013), the Consumer Behaviour Model first begins with a marketing stimulus plus some other stimulus which is assimilated by the individual consumer, which subsequently leads to the buying decision process, and thereafter to the decision to purchase.

Applying this model to a fad/pyramid scheme gives the following:

- The consumer hears about the scheme through some form of marketing stimulus—either word-of mouth advertising by friends and family, or via an invitation on social media or email (Kotler et al. 2013; Shen, Zhang & Zhao, 2016).

Simultaneously, another environmental stimulus is acting upon the consumer, such as a failing or stalled economy, financial regulations that make it hard to access loans, or even high unemployment rates (Appel 2008; Kotler et al. 2013; Loudenback & Jackson 2018).

- These two stimuli are interpreted and analysed subjectively according to the consumer's own psychological makeup, such as their motivations and perceptions, as well as all the cultural, social, and personal characteristics which makes that consumer a unique individual (Kotler et al. 2013).
- Once the stimuli have been assimilated by the consumer, the buying process begins:

- The consumer recognises that they have a problem, for instance, not enough money to pay bills and the fad's offering seems too good to be true (Appel 2008; Kotler et al. 2013; Loudenback and Jackson 2018).
- Next comes information search, where the consumer tries to get more information on the fad, such as through forums, chats, social media pages, and so on (Chen, Wang and Xie 2011 as cited in Shen et al. 2016; Kotler et al. 2013).
- The consumer then evaluates the alternative sources of short-term finance and weighs the pros and cons of each option against those of the fad (Kotler et al. 2013).
- Thereafter the consumer decides whether they will buy in to the scheme or not (Kotler et al. 2013; Shen et al. 2016). For instance, if the evaluation shows that they cannot raise a significant sum of cash to pay a certain bill at a certain time, and that taking a chance on the scheme might be worth the risk, the consumer may then decide to go ahead and join the scheme.
- The consumer then actually joins the fad having already made up their mind as to their decision (Kotler et al. 2013). (See Figure 5)

Figure 5. Application of the Consumer Behaviour Model to a fad (Adapted from Kotler et al. 2013, 196).

The Consumer Behaviour Model *presumes that consumers are rational beings* that always make logical and informed decisions (Ariely 2009; Kotler et al. 2013). But this is rarely ever the case; there are many instances where consumers make irrational decisions based solely on feelings, emotions, and instincts and not on logic and reason (Ariely 2009; Kotler et al. 2013; Shen et al. 2016).

These irrational decisions, as explained by Ariely (2009), are caused by *optimism bias* - where persons are quick to believe that a favourable outcome will happen regardless of their decision. All these feelings and beliefs motivate a person to make the purchase or not (Shen et al. 2016).

Motivation makes up one of the aspects of consumer psychology, and motivation theories have commonly been used to explain Fad behaviour. These will be discussed next.

2.9.2 Motivation Theories. Kotler et al. (2013), on page 196, mentions that humans are driven by both *biogenic* and *psychogenic needs* arising from physiological and psychological tension states, which coincides with the need to relieve physical discomforts such as hunger, and to relieve psychological discomforts such as feeling the need to belong, respectively. These needs, when they become *sufficiently and intensely aroused, becomes a motive, or driving force, compelling a person to act* (Kotler et al. 2013).

By far, the most widely used and easily applied motivation theories for understanding fad behaviour are those postulated by Maslow, Herzberg, and Freud.

Maslow's hierarchy of needs, for instance, postulates that human needs are hierarchical in nature with physical/biogenic needs forming the base of the hierarchy and psychological/psychogenic needs higher up (Kotler et al. 2013; McLeod 2018). Human needs are filled from the most urgent to the least urgent, and only when that particular need is a filled can the person move on to satisfy the next important need (Kotler et al. 2013; McLeod 2018). The hierarchical order in which these needs are satisfied are solely dependent on the particular individual as all humans may be on different levels of need at the same point in time (Kotler et al. 2013; McLeod 2018).

On the other hand, *Herzberg's two-factor theory*, postulates that persons are motivated by the presence of factors that causes them satisfaction (*satisfiers*) and not necessarily by the absence of *dissatisfiers* (Kotler et al. 2013).

While both Maslow and Herzberg assumes that a person *knows*, or is *conscious of*, what he needs, *Sigmund Freud* disagrees. In fact, he contends that “the psychological forces shaping a person’s behaviour are *largely unconscious*, and that a person *cannot fully understand his or her own motivations*.” (Kotler et al. 2013, 196).

The implications of the above theories for fads are clear. Fads tend to target, or rather *take advantage* of, some unmet physiological or psychological need such as, purchasing food or seeking to belong to some group (Appel 2008). Additionally, persons who encourage others to join fads may *focus on the presence of satisfiers* within the fad such as instant physical gratification—obtaining fast cash. However, with Freuds’ theory in mind, sometimes persons

just *unconsciously* join a fad, with no real reasonable explanation – they simply go with the flow.

While going with the flow may suffice as a reasonable explanation for some, it is insufficient for most, therefore requiring more investigation. Other theories have since been proposed to understand these “largely unconscious” psychological forces (Kotler et al. 2013, 196) such as, information adoption, information cascades, and herd behaviour. These will be discussed in the following paragraphs.

2.9.3 Behavioural Theories. Information plays a critical role in the buying decision process and is imperative for elucidating fad behaviour. Shen et al. (2016) on page 604, defines *information adoption* as a process whereby *individuals internalise the information they receive in order to improve their decision-making behaviour*. In order for persons to accept the information as credible and act upon it, they must first perceive the information as being useful – that is, it must have “high argument quality and is provided by credible sources” (Shen et al. 2016, 606).

With respect to fad behaviour, this will come into play in the second stage of the buying behaviour process where the individual is seeking more information on the fad. If the information comes from a credible source, such as an opinion leader, or a close family or friend, the individual may be more inclined to accept this information as true. However, not only must the source be credible, but the argument for the fad must be compelling. (See Figure 6)

BUYING DECISION PROCESS

Figure 6. Information Adoption Model integrated into Buying Decision Process for a Fad (Adapted from Kotler et al. 2013, 196 and Wang 2016, 618).

Interestingly, some scholars view information adoption as a type of “*informational influence*”, that is, credible information as received by others, is used to influence another person’s decision (Shen et al. 2016, 604).

Another theory that highlights the influence of information on fad behaviour, is *information cascades*. This theory posits that “*the actions of early individuals can influence the behaviour of others so that later individuals ignore their own information and merely follow suit*” (Bikhchandani, Hirshleifer and Welch 1992, 1004). For instance, if a Contractor is rejected by one major Company, then he is more likely to be rejected by subsequent companies once they have heard of his rejection, despite their limited knowledge of the details surrounding his first rejection. Likewise, in a fad, later individuals choose to reject their own knowledge and to accept the decision of an early influencer/expert (Bikhchandani, Hirshleifer & Welch, 1998).

This is a much different situation from *peer pressure* which implies that an individual is **forced** to adopt someone else's decision/behaviour, whereas in the cascade, the individual clearly makes a choice (Bikhchandani et al. 1992).

This theory is also different from information adoption, where the individual internalises the information received, whereas with information cascades, the individual is abdicating this information internalisation process to others and imitating their decision. The latter is more likely to occur in instances where the individual is doubtful about the accuracy of his own decision, and so becomes susceptible to the informational influence of those he views as being better informed, that is, opinion leaders/experts (Deutsch and Gerard 1955, as cited in Bikhchandani et al. 1992; Bikhchandani et al. 1998).

Information cascades are also more likely to occur in “online environments” such as, social media sites, where 1) individuals may be lacking accurate information, 2) many suitable substitutes may be available, and 3) it is easy to get a lot of information regarding others' previous choices (Shen et al. 2016, 2756)

In examining fad behaviour, it is important to note that *information cascades do not last forever* (Bikhchandani et al. 1998). Cascades are not built upon a strong foundation and are therefore vulnerable to “small shocks” which can “lead to large shifts in behaviour” (Bikhchandani et al. 1992, 993). So, if any new information is supplied to the cascade, no matter how small, it can cause large changes in mass behaviour thereby changing the direction of the cascade (Bikhchandani et al. 1992, 1998). The implication of this for fads is that, as new, oftentimes contradictory, information becomes available, people will shift towards something else, therefore shortening the life of the fad.

Furthermore, informational cascades can lead to *herd behaviour*. Herd behaviour occurs when an individual imitates the behaviour and decisions of others, while ignoring his own private information (Balcilar and Demirer 2015; Bikhchandani et al. 1998; Chong, Liu and Zhu 2017; Morone and Samanidou 2008; Shen et al. 2016). As simply explained by Shen et al. (2016) on page 2756, it is a conscious disregard for one's own information and “imitating others.” It is as one Philosopher famously wrote, “*when people are free to do as they please, they usually imitate each other*” (Hoffer,1955, as cited in Bikhchandani et al. 1998, 152). This innate predisposition to imitate others has also been recognised and acknowledged by many researchers over the years such as, Balcilar and Demirer (2015), Bikhchandani et al. (1998), Chong et al. (2017), Morone and Samanidou (2008), and Shen et al. (2016) to name a few.

Herd behaviour is also believed to occur when no new information is being supplied to the cascade, and people begin imitating each other solely on the premise that the majority of people cannot be wrong (*Bandwagon effect*), or because of their esteem/psychogenic need to belong/be accepted (Balcilar and Demirer 2015; Bikhchandani et al. 1998; Chong et al. 2017; Kotler et al. 2013; McLeod 2018; Morone and Samanidou 2008; Shen et al. 2016).

Additionally, herding could also spring from a person's *risk preference*. Risk preference, as defined by one researcher is "*the propensity to engage in behaviours or activities that are rewarding yet involve some potential for loss*" (Steinberg 2013, as cited in Mata et al. 2018, 156). In economics, these rewards and losses are often monetary and risk preference is basically concerned with the return of investment (Mata et al. 2018). While one could reasonably expect risk-takers to jump at the opportunity to gain a larger return on their small investment, surprisingly, even risk-averse individuals can make decisions that leads to herding. As explained by Parrish (2020, 33) *risk averse* persons, that is, non-risk-takers, due to their irrational "fear of being alone or losing out," might cope with such fear by imitating the decisions/behaviours of others.

For fads therefore, herding may result simply because persons are seeing/hearing what others are doing, or because they want to be a part of the group, or because they fear being left out.

Having examined the literature to ascertain the various causes of fad behaviour, this paper will now discuss the methodological approach used for capturing data to explore the sou/pyramid phenomenon.

3. METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION

This multiple-methods research was guided by Subjectivist Ontology and Interpretivist Epistemology which opines that the reality of existing social phenomena is heavily influenced by how individual social actors perceive and interpret them and it is the understanding of these varying views and interpretations that “constitutes acceptable knowledge” (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2012, 132).

In accordance with the above, this researcher relied heavily upon *Participant Observation* in order to answer the research question. This helped the researcher to understand the citizens’ actions, motives, and intentions, and to see things from their points of view (Saunders et al. 2012). The major benefit of this method was that this researcher was directly able to observe and interact with participants unhindered in their natural environment, that is, on the social media app, Telegram (www.telegram.org).

Additionally, the author used an abductive approach (theory modification), to fully explore the phenomenon and to modify existing fad theory as it relates to pyramid schemes (Saunders et al. 2012). In using this approach, the author was able to gather theoretical clues as to why people were getting caught up in the fad, and then using these theories the author was able to devise a questionnaire to test them. However, coming out of the questionnaires arose other theoretical subjects that could explain the sou sou fad behaviour, and the author had to revise the literature review to touch on these additional subjects.

3.1 Data Collection

Both primary and secondary sources of data collection were collected. Secondary sources were found mostly in academic journals (of economics), marketing textbooks as well as online newspaper articles, while Participant Observation was used as the main primary data collection method, alongside a questionnaire. (See *Appendix 3*)

Over a three-week period, the author joined about 15 different sou sou groups on the Telegram app. At the end of three weeks, a link to the survey (a Google Form) was sent to each of the 15 different sou sou groups (two had over 3500 members each, three had over 100 members, and the rest had less than 25 members).

The survey link was also sent to 70 individuals from all the groups to ensure maximum participation in the survey. The participants were non-randomly chosen for the sample according to the researcher’s judgement, such as persons who were online (on the Telegram

app) at the time, or who had last read their chat within 24 hours of the link being posted. This was done because the researcher wanted to ensure that the link was seen and completed by active members of the various sou sou communities.

Five days later, their responses were collected and collated. (See *Appendix 4*) Despite being sent to a wide cross-section of people, in total, only 28 persons chose to complete the survey within the short time frame. Their results are discussed in the next section.

4.1.2 Sou Sou Operations. The detailed process for operating the sou sou boards are presented in *Appendix 1*.

Basically, the board opens with a core group, and is filled with new recruits who gift their money to the core (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020). Appendix 2 shows the payment schemes for the most popular groups. (See *Appendix 2*)

Core members also re-gift a portion of their money to the one who recruited them (“Joel M Upliftment” 2020). The board then splits into new groups and the process restarts (“Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020).

The number of recruits needed to close each board, as well as the number of groups formed after each board splits for a typical 63-person board and a 20-person board are shown in Figures 9 and 10 below.

Figure 9. Board splits and Recruits needed for a typical 63-person board. (“Keston G 63k crew” 2020).

Figure 10. Board splits and Recruits needed for a typical 20-person board. (“Joel M Upliftment” 2020).

From the figures shown, one can clearly see that both boards split exponentially, from 8^1 , to 8^8 , to 8^{64} , to 8^{512} , to 8^{4096} (in the 63-person board), and from 4^1 , 4^4 , 4^{16} , 4^{64} , and 4^{256} (in the 20-person board); each split requiring more and more recruits to close off the boards. In the 63-person board, 56 recruits are required for the first split, while 3,584 recruits are required for the third split (“Keston G 63k crew” 2020). In the 20-person board, however, only 16 recruits are required for the first split, with 256 recruits needed for the third (“Joel M Upliftment” 2020).

4.2 Characteristics of pyramid schemes versus the current sou sou schemes

The table below lists the characteristics of a typical pyramid scheme and checks it against the characteristics of the current sou sou schemes in Trinidad and Tobago. (See Table 2 below)

Table 2. Characteristics of typical pyramid schemes versus the current sou sou schemes

Main characteristics of a pyramid scheme	Shown in current sou sou schemes?	Details
1. Recruits are promised a high pay-out in return for a small investment of money (Gonzales 2020).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	All recruits must gift to their respective core person at the end of week zero, with the promise of gaining thousands of dollars in a few weeks’ time (“Keston G 63k crew” 2020).

2. The sole emphasis is on recruitment and not the sale of products (Gonzales 2020).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	All recruits are encouraged to bring one person when they join, and that person must also bring their one person, and so on (“Keston G 63k crew” 2020).
3. Early investors are paid from the monies contributed by new recruits (Gonzales 2020).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	New recruits must gift to their core person, who regifts a portion of that same money to their core person, and so on (“Keston G 63k crew” 2020).
4. The pyramid collapses when the pool of new recruits shrinks or stalls (Gonzales 2020).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Usually after the third splits, it becomes increasingly hard to fill the boards (that is 512 groups for a 63-person board, or 64 groups for a 20-person board).
5. The vast majority of recruits will never be paid (Gonzales 2020).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Most persons who joined sou sou groups have seen their boards stall. With no new members joining the groups, the boards cannot get the required numbers to fill...so it never closes, therefore the core members of these boards never get their promised gifts (“Keston G 63k crew” 2020)

4.3 Survey Results

This section discusses the results from the survey as detailed in *Appendix 4*.

According to the survey:

- Most (28%) of the respondents were between the ages of 31 and 50, with an average age of 34.
- Eighty-two percent of the respondents were female, with 46% of respondents having at least high school qualifications.
- The majority (21.4%) of the respondents were self-employed, 17.9% were Clerks, 14.3% were in the protective forces, and 10.7% were managers.
- The number of sou sou groups that the respondents joined, ranged from 1 to 16, with respondents joining on average, five sou sou groups.
- Respondents’ main reasons for joining the sou sou was to make extra money (reported by over half of the respondents) as well as to clear off their debts (reported by 17.9% of respondents).
- Nearly all the participants (92.8%) were invited by family and friends. Only one person interestingly was not contacted by anyone, but saw an ad, and decided to join.
- Respondents were initially contacted to join the sou mainly via word of mouth (reported by over half of the respondents), and through social media (reported by 35.7%).
- The sou sou process was explained to the majority (75%) of the respondents before they joined.
- The majority (86%) of the respondents knew about the risks of the sou sou before they joined.
- With respect to what the respondents liked most about the sou sou, half of them reported liking the large return on their investment, as well as the fast cash as well as the networking with other people (reported by 14.3%).

- However, with respect to what the respondents disliked the most about the sou sou, 46.7% of the people had a problem with the board stalling or crashing, and 46.7% also had a problem with the people in the groups, specifically, that some were dishonest, greedy, selfish, and lazy.
- An overwhelming majority (93%) of the respondents did invite others to join - family and friends – with 96% of these invited ones becoming new recruits.
- The respondents were able to attract new recruits mainly by explaining the process to them and by showing them the money they collected.
- Most (64%) of the respondents made money from the sou sou – with half of them making between \$100 to \$10,000, with only one person making between \$50,100 to \$60,000.
- However, a lot more respondents (68%) reported losing money in the sou sou, with 84% of respondents reportedly losing between \$1 to \$3000, with only one person losing between \$12,001 to \$15,000.
- Interestingly, over half (57%) of the respondents were active members of their various sou sou groups.
- The majority (68%) of respondents indicated that even if they had known all that they currently know about the sou sou, they would have still joined as they felt it was worth the risk.
- Despite this, only 64% of them would recommend that others join the sou sou, which is exactly the same figures received for those who made money from the sou sou.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

5.1 Analysis of the results

1. Analysis of the results suggests that *the sou sou schemes in Trinidad and Tobago are in fact pyramid schemes that are attracting mainly working-class (18 to 45 years old) females.*
2. The survey findings (in Appendix 4) point to the major biogenic needs that are motivating these people to join the sou sou that is, to make extra money, to obtain fast cash, to clear outstanding debts, for overall financial assistance, and to start a business. These biogenic needs correspond to what Maslow describes as physiological and safety needs (Kotler et al. 2012; McLeod 2018).
3. The survey findings identified the main psychological/psychogenic needs that are motivating people to join the sou sou that is, to network and to work together, according to 14.3% of the respondents. These psychogenic needs correspond to what Maslow described as love and belonging needs (Kotler et al. 2012; McLeod 2018).

The survey findings are significant when placed within the wider environmental context.

In 2020 the country was already plagued by a stalling economy due to falling oil prices, large influx of illegal immigrants competing for limited jobs, increased unemployment impeding many from providing their families, increased food and gas prices in turn increasing the cost of living, and then the Covid-19 pandemic came (Caribbean National Weekly 2020; Loop News 2020a, 2020b; Ministry of Health Trinidad and Tobago n.d.; Taitt 2020). For months, many non-essential businesses were forced closed while most citizens had to survive on a reduced income; many could not afford the basic necessities neither pay their debts (Ministry of Health Trinidad and Tobago n.d.; Taitt 2020). The self-employed/Sole Traders, who interestingly made up the majority (21.4%) of the survey respondents suffered most (Ministry of Social Development and Family Services 2020; Sookram and Wolffe-O'Neil 2020). Now that the country is slowly opening back up for business, many persons are still in survival mode, and are constantly seeking more money (Sambrano 2020).

Furthermore, the Covid-19 pandemic restricted the gathering of people and isolated loved ones from each other; this would have taken a toll on citizens' mental state (Ministry of Health Trinidad and Tobago n.d.; WHO 2020). As social actors they would have craved for the company of others, especially their family and friends (Saunders et al. 2012). It is, therefore, unsurprising that the various sou sou groups were comprised of a large community (93%) of

the respondents' friends and family. This enabled them to feel close to each other, even if they were physically apart.

Moreover, being active in the various sou sou groups and volunteering to update the boards (reported by 57% of the respondents), would have also filled respondents' psychogenic need for esteem—that is, status and recognition among their peers (Kotler et al. 2012; McLeod 2018).

5.2 Answering the research questions

Therefore, in answering the other research questions posed earlier:

1. The main physiological determinants of this sou sou fad are inferred as being (in decreasing order of severity) **environmental factors** such as, *nationwide Covid-19 restrictions causing extreme hardship to individuals and businesses, increased unemployment and job cuts impeding many from providing for their families, and increased food and gas prices in turn increasing the cost of living.*

2. The main psychological determinants are interpreted as being the motivation to fill their unmet:

- **Physiological needs** (need for food, clothing, and shelter)
- **Safety needs** (need for gainful employment)
- **Love needs** (need for interpersonal interactions and relationships with family and friends)
- **Belonging needs and/or risk preference** (need to be a part of something and/or a fear of being left behind)
- **Esteem needs** (need to be recognised among their peers)

These needs would have all heightened and peaked during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The fact that the majority of persons (68%) knew about the sou sou's operations as well as its risk, but still joined anyway, seems to validate what the literature reveals about how information adoption, information cascades, and herding influences fad behaviour. The overwhelming majority (96.4%) of respondents verified that the information they received was from people they felt were credible, that is friends and family (*source credibility*) – and that these people explained to them how the sou sou works (*argument quality*) – which led them to adopt and internalise that information, along with their own information regarding the risks, which they then used to make their decision to join.

Additionally, since 21% of those recruited saw their friends and family actually got pay-outs, this led them to ignore their own information regarding the risks, and to imitate others' decision to join, thereby starting an information cascade, which subsequently led to herd behaviour by others later on.

5.3 Application of the consumer behaviour model to fads

Therefore, applying the Consumer Behaviour Model for fads to the sou sou scheme gives the following:

- a) The consumer hears about the scheme through some form of *marketing stimulus* – either word-of mouth advertising by friends and family, social media ads or by seeing others collect their pay-outs. Simultaneously, *other stimuli* such as Covid-19 restrictions, increased unemployment and food prices is acting upon the consumer
- b) These two stimuli are interpreted and analysed subjectively according to the consumer's unique personal characteristics, such as their risk preference, as well as their psychological makeup, especially their motivation to fill their physiological, safety, love and belonging, and esteem needs.
- c) Once the stimuli have been assimilated by the consumer, the buying process begins:
 - The consumer recognises that they have a problem, that is, *some unmet biogenic or psychogenic need* that only the sou sou could satisfy.
 - Next, the consumer seeks more information on the sou sou. There is some compelling argument for the sou sou that is usually provided by family and friends which is useful to the consumer, who then accepts, adopts, and internalises this information. However, ***this is where the buying decision process essentially breaks down***. Some consumers choose to ignore their own information about the sou sou's risks, and imitate others' decision to join, therefore starting an information cascade.
 - This then leads to *herd behaviour*, as other consumers further along join the sou sou simply because others are.

This is demonstrated by Figure 11.

Figure 11. Consumer Buying Behaviour Model of the hybrid sou sou/pyramid scheme. (Adapted from Kotler et al, 2012).

The above discussion is made in light of the limitations of this research.

5.4 Limitations of this research

As much as this research tried to improve its quality by being credible and objective (reliable) to some point, the very nature of this unique research does not allow for the study to follow strict and robust methodologies as would be expected of scientific or most case research (Saunders et al., 2012; Yin, 2009). This mostly qualitative research only focused on a very narrow aspect of human behaviour and from a mainly marketing perspective, however, there are other behavioural theories regarding risk acceptance, from the field of behavioural finance, and even more theories on group dynamics that could have been applied to this phenomenon as well. Future studies can focus on these additional perspectives as well as take on a more rigid quantitative approach to data collection and analysis to make the study more robust.

The next section concludes this paper.

6. CONCLUSION

This research investigated the sou sou fad in Trinidad and Tobago and found that the sou sou groups were indeed pyramid schemes and that the *environmental factors* causing people to join the sou sou were: the Covid-19 restrictions, increased unemployment and job cuts, and increased food and gas prices (Caribbean National Weekly 2020; Loop News 2020a, 2020b; Ministry of Health Trinidad and Tobago n.d.; Ministry of Social Development and Family Services 2020; Sambrano 2020; Sookram and Wolffe-O'Neil 2020; Taitt 2020).

In addition, there were *psychological factors* such as, motivation to fill their unmet needs for food, clothing, and shelter, to be gainfully employed, to have meaningful interactions and relationships with family and friends, to be a part of something, and to be recognised among their peers.

These needs would have all heightened and peaked during the Covid-19 pandemic (Ministry of Health Trinidad and Tobago n.d.; WHO 2020).

The results also validated what the extant literature reveals about how information adoption, information cascades, and herding, influences fad behaviour (Balcilar and Demirer 2015; Bikhchandani et al. 1992, 1998; Chong et al. 2017; Morone and Samanidou 2008; Shen et al. 2016; Wang 2016).

Finally, the Consumer Behaviour Model for a fad, was applied to the sou sou using the findings.

In closing, the purpose of this research, as mentioned in the introduction, was achieved.

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APPENDIX 1. DETAILED SOU SOU OPERATIONS

Board opens -

In the 63-persons board, the board opens with seven (7) persons in the centre making up the “core” (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020). The board has 56 empty spots that needs to be filled by the core, therefore, each core member is responsible for ensuring that their eight (8) spots are filled (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020). However, the logic behind filling the board is that one person invites one person, who invites one person, and so on, until the board is filled (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020). Potential recruits are typically invited to join the sou sou group on the Telegram app, via a private link (“Gopi 28k(Keston G), 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020).

Board closes -

When the board is “closed”, the “gifting” period begins; each board is colour coded so that persons outside the core would gift their money to their respective core person, and would continue to gift that same person for the life of the sou sou. (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020). So, each core member would therefore receive eight (8) gifts each gifting period (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020). Receipts are given upon payment, and pictures of it are taken by all parties and posted to the group for payment verification (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020).

Board splits -

Once all core members have been paid, the board splits into eight (8) new groups with persons from the three colours (1 yellow, 2 orange and 4 green) making up the new core members (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020). Once their boards are closed and these core members are paid, they must re-gift a part of their payment to the person they gifted the first time (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020).

Unlike in a traditional sou sou, there is no “banker” or administrator who holds the members’ cash on any of the boards, but each person on the board holds on to their cash until gifting begins and each individual contacts their gifting person to organise meeting place and time for completing the payment transaction (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020). Various members of the group volunteer to update the board with names, to list the pay-out details, as well as to aid the splitting of the boards, so that operations run

smoothly (“Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020).

The workings are similar for the 20-person board however, it is smaller, with a core of four (4) persons, each responsible for recruiting four (4) individual each (“Joel M Upliftment” 2020). Since this board has less people to recruit, it often fills faster, resulting in people being gifted earlier (“Joel M Upliftment” 2020). However, persons are gifted less money than on the bigger boards (“Joel M Upliftment” 2020).

APPENDIX 2. DETAILED PAYMENT SCHEMES FOR THE POPULAR BOARDS

Payments Schemes

Many sou sou groups offer various payment schemes. Some of the popular ones are: Keston G 63k crew, Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group, Joel M Upliftment, Team Dulaire 100 63k crew, and Gopi 28k(Keston G). These are all shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1. The most popular sou sou schemes and their payments

Board type	63-person	63-person	16-person	63-person	63-person
Week 0	Gift \$700	Gift \$500	Gift \$350	Gift \$175	Gift \$100
Week 1	Receive \$5600 Regift \$3500 Keep \$2100	Receive \$4000 Regift \$3000 Keep \$1000	Receive \$1400 Regift \$700 Keep \$700	Receive \$1400 Regift \$700 Keep \$700	Receive \$800 Regift \$700 Keep \$100
Week 2	Receive \$28,000 Regift \$17,500 Keep \$10,500	Receive \$24,000 Keep \$24,000	Receive \$2800 Regift \$1400 Keep \$1400	Receive \$5600 Regift \$3500 Keep \$2100	Receive \$5600 Regift \$3500 Keep \$2100
Week 3	Receive \$140,000 Regift \$42,000 Keep \$98,000	-	Receive \$5600 Regift \$2100 Keep \$3500	Receive \$28,000 Regift \$11,500 Keep \$10,500	Receive \$28,000 Keep \$28,000
Week 4	Receive \$336,000 Keep \$336,000	-	Receive \$8400 Regift \$2800 Keep \$5600	Receive \$92,000 Regift \$42,000 Keep \$50,000	-
Week 5	-	-	Receive \$11,200 Keep \$11,200	Receive \$336,000 Keep \$336,000	-
Total \$ gained	\$398,600	\$25,000	\$22,400	\$399,300	\$30,200
Sou Sou Name	Keston G 63k crew	Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group	Joel M Upliftment	Team Dulaire 100 63k crew	Gopi 28k(Keston G)

Source: “Gopi 28k(Keston G)” 2020; J. Garcia personal communication, October 30, 2020; “Jean’s 63K Crew Foundation Group” 2020; “Joel M Upliftment” 2020; “Keston G 63k crew” 2020.

Note: All monies quoted are in TT\$

APPENDIX 3. SOU SOU QUESTIONNAIRE

This survey is being carried out as part of a research study, by a MPhil/Ph.D student of the University of Trinidad and Tobago, to understand the popularity of the “Sou Sou” fad in Trinidad. Your participation is totally voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time. Should you answer all the survey questions you will qualify to be part of a random draw for a CASH prize of \$100.

This short survey is intended for those who have joined a sou sou this year, and should only take about 5 minutes to complete. Please answer ALL the questions as honestly and freely as possible. The information you provide will be kept strictly confidential and anonymous and will ONLY be used for academic purposes.

Thank you in advance for your responses! Your participation is greatly appreciated!

1. Age (please type a number) ...
2. Gender (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response)– Male
 female
3. Current education level (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) – High School Undergraduate qualification Post graduate qualification
4. Current Job Title ...
5. How many sou sou groups did you join? (please type a number) ...
6. Why did you join the sou? ...
7. Who invited you the first time to join the sou? ...
8. How were you initially contacted to join? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Word of mouth Phone call SMS Text message Social media
9. Did the person who invited you explain everything about the sou sou BEFORE you joined? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No
10. Did you know about the risks of the sou sou before joining? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No
11. What do you like most about the sou sou? ...
12. What do you DISLIKE most about the sou sou? ...
13. Did you invite other people to join the sou sou with you? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No
- 13.a WHO did you invite? ...
- 13.b Did they join the sou sou? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No
- 13.b. i. HOW did you get them to join? ...
14. Did you make money from the sou sou? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No

14. a How much money did you make? (please type a number) ... Dollars

15. Did you lose money in the sou sou? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No

15.a How much money did you lose? (please type a number) ... Dollars

16. Were/are you an active member of your board? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No

17. Would you say that the sou sou is worth the risk? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No

18. if you knew what you know now about the sou sou, would you still have joined? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No

19. Would you recommend that people join the sou? (Please tick the appropriate box. You may only choose one response) Yes No

Thank you for your responses. You now qualify to win a \$100 cash prize. You will, however, need to submit your contact number so that you may be notified should you win. Your contact number will not be used in any way to identify you or to spam you.

APPENDIX 4. SOU SOU RESPONSES

1. What is your age? (in years)

Age Group	Frequency	Percentages	
18-30	8		28%
31-50	19		68%
51-70	1		4%
Total	28	100%	
Average	34 years		

2. What is your gender?

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	5	18%
Female	23	82%
Total	23	100%

3. What is your current education level?

Education Level	Frequency	Percentage
High School	13	46%
Undergraduate	8	29%
Postgraduate	7	25%
Total	28	100%

4. What is your current job title?

Respondents Job	Frequency	Percentage
Protective services	4	14.30%
Self employed	6	21.40%
Manager	3	10.70%
Hairdressing	1	3.60%
Taxi driver	1	3.60%
Clerk	5	17.90%
Networking	1	3.60%
Joiner	1	3.60%
Chef	1	3.60%
Public Servant	1	3.60%
Teacher Assistant	1	3.60%
SWFO 1	1	3.60%
Student	1	3.60%
Junior Admin Asst	1	3.60%
Total	28	100%

5. How many sou sou groups did your join?

No. of groups joined	Frequency	Percentage
1	3	10.70%
2	6	21.40%
3	2	7.15%
4	4	14.30%
5	6	21.40%
6	0	0%
7	2	7.15%
8	1	3.60%
9	0	0%
10	2	7.15%
11	0	0%
12	0	0%
13	0	0%
14	0	0%
15	1	3.60%
16	1	3.60%
Total	28	100%
Average	5.125	

6. Why did you join the sou sou?

Reason for joining sou sou	Frequency	Percentage
To make (extra) money	15	53.60%
For financial Assistance	3	10.70%
To clear debts	5	17.90%
To start a business	2	7.15%
Investment	1	3.60%
To see if it was true	2	7.15%
Total	28	100%

7. Who invited you the first time to join the sou?

Who invited you to join?	Frequency	Percentage
Friends and Family	26	92.80%
Co-worker	1	3.60%
No one. Saw an Ad.	1	3.60%
Total	28	100%

Who invited Respondent to join sou sou

■ Friends and Family ■ Coworker ■ No one. Saw an Ad.

8. How were you initially contacted to join?

How were you initially contacted to join?	Frequency	Percentage
Social Media	10	35.70%
Word of mouth	15	53.60%
phone call	2	7.15%
Social Media AND word of mouth	1	3.60%
Total	28	100%

How Respondents were 1st contacted to join

■ Social Media ■ Word of mouth ■ phone call ■ Social Media AND word of mouth

9. Did the person who invited you explain everything about the sou sou BEFORE you joined?

Was the Sou Sou fully explained to you before joining?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	21	75%
No	7	25%

Total

28

100%

Was sou sou fully explained to Respondent before they joined?

10. Did you know about the risks of the sou sou BEFORE joining?

Did Respondent know about the risks before joining?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	24	86%
No	4	14%
Total	28	100%

Did Respondent know about the risks before joining?

11. What do you like most about the sou sou?

What Respondent liked most about sou sou	Frequency	Percentage
The large return on investment	14	50%
Networking with people	4	14.30%
Fast cash	5	17.90%
Being financially free	1	3.60%
It could work if people are honest	1	3.60%

Nothing. It's a scam	1	3.60%
Easy to get the cash	2	7.15%
Total	28	100%

12. What do you DISLIKE the most about the sou sou?

What Respondents disliked most about the sou sou	Frequency	Main Groupings	Frequency2	Percentage
Inviting people	2	Problems with board crashing or stalling	14	45.20%
Annoying Admins	1	Problems with people in the group	14	45.20%
Dishonest people	7	Nothing	1	3.10%
When it crashes	5	Recruiting others	2	6.50%
Too long to get pay out	6	Total	31	
When people don't work to bring in others	3			
Greedy people	2			
Zero transparency	1			
Nothing	1			
Not getting money or refund	3			

13. Did you invite other people to join the sou sou with you?

Did respondent invite others to join sou sou?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	26	93.00%
No	2	7.00%
Total	28	100%

13.a WHO did you invite?

Who did the respondent invite?	Frequency	Percentage
Friends and Family	26	93%
Friends, Family and Co-workers	1	3.50%
Everyone	1	3.50%

Total	28	100%
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13.b Did they join the sou sou?

Did the Respondents' invitees join the sou sou?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	25	96.00%
No	1	4.00%
Total	26	100%

13.c HOW did you get them to join the sou sou?

How did Respondent get them to join?	Frequency	Percentage
Asked them	2	8%
Showed them the money	5	21%
Explained it to them	9	38%

Sent them a link	1	4%
Persuaded them	3	13%
Added them	2	8%
Word of mouth	2	8%

Total 24 100%

14. Did you make any money from the sou sou?

Did Respondent make money from the sou sou ?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	18	64%
No	10	36%
Total	28	100%

14.a How much money did you make? (In TT\$)

How much money did Respondent make?	Frequency	Percentage
\$100 to \$10,000	9	50%
\$10,100 to \$20,000	6	33%
\$20,100 to \$30,000	2	11%
\$30,100 to \$40,000	0	0%
\$40,100 to \$50,000	0	0%
\$50,100 to \$60,000	1	6%
Total	18	100%

15. Did you lose money in the sou sou?

Did Respondents lose money in the sou sou?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	19	68%
No	9	32%
Total	28	100%

15.a How much money did you lose? (In TT\$)

How much money did respondents lose?	Frequency	Percentage
\$1 to \$3000	16	84%
\$3001 to \$6000	2	11%
\$6001 to \$9000	0	0%
\$9001 to \$12,000	0	0%
\$12,001 to \$15,000	1	5%
Total	19	100%

16. Were/are you an active member of your sou sou board?

Were Respondents active in their sou sou boards?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	16	57%
No	12	43%
Total	28	100%

17. Would you say that the sou sou is worth the risk?

Do Respondents feel that sou sou is worth the risks?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	19	68%
No	9	32%
Total	28	100%

18. If you knew what you know now about the sou sou, would you still have joined?

If Respondents knew what they know now about the sou sou, would they still have joined?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	19	68%
No	9	32%
Total	28	100%

19. Would you recommend that other people join the sou sou?

Would Respondent recommend that others join the sou sou?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	18	64%
No	10	36%
Total	28	100%

Do Respondents recommend that others join the sou sou?

